

Minireview

The Crucial Role of Gut Microbiota in Disease Prevention

Simone Cristoni¹ and Giovanni Puccio²

1. I.S.B. – Ion Source & Biotechnologies, Milan, Italy
2. Emmanuele association, Palermo, Italy

Introduction and discussion

The importance of maintaining a healthy gut microbiota cannot be overstated, as it plays a vital role in preventing a wide range of diseases, including diabetes, obesity, cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and psychological disorders.¹⁻⁵ A balanced gut microbiota is essential for optimal health, and a disruption in this delicate balance, known as intestinal dysbiosis, can lead to adverse consequences.

Metabolic gut microbiota dysbiosis⁶ has been linked to the development of type 2 diabetes and obesity.^{1,2} An imbalance in the gut's microbial composition can negatively affect metabolic functions, leading to insulin resistance and impaired glucose homeostasis. Furthermore, the gut microbiota has been implicated in regulating appetite and energy metabolism, with dysbiosis contributing to weight gain and obesity.

Cardiovascular diseases, such as atherosclerosis and hypertension, have also been associated with gut dysbiosis. The gut microbiota produces metabolites, like trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO), which can promote inflammation and contribute to the development of cardiovascular diseases. Therefore, maintaining a balanced gut microbiota may reduce the risk of cardiovascular events.

The gut microbiota has a significant impact on the immune system and inflammation, making it a key player in cancer prevention. Intestinal dysbiosis can lead to chronic inflammation, which has been implicated in the initiation and progression of various cancers. A healthy gut microbiota may help maintain a balanced immune response, reducing the risk of cancer development.

Psychological disorders, such as anxiety and depression, have also been linked to gut dysbiosis. The gut-brain axis is a complex communication network connecting the enteric nervous system with the central nervous system. Imbalances in the gut microbiota can disrupt this communication, leading to altered neurotransmitter production, increased inflammation, and impaired stress response, all of which can contribute to the development of psychological disorders.

Conclusion

In conclusion, maintaining a balanced gut microbiota is essential for preventing a diverse array of diseases, from metabolic disorders to cancer and psychological illnesses. A healthy diet, regular exercise, and the use of prebiotics and probiotics can help promote a healthy gut microbiota, ultimately improving overall health and reducing the risk of disease.

References

1. Gurung M, Li Z, You H, Rodrigues R, Jump DB, Morgun A, Shulzhenko N. Role of gut microbiota in type 2 diabetes pathophysiology. *EBioMedicine*. **2020** Jan;51:102590. doi: 10.1016/j.ebiom.2019.11.051.
2. Liu BN, Liu XT, Liang ZH, Wang JH. Gut microbiota in obesity. *World J Gastroenterol*. **2021** Jul 7;27(25):3837-3850. doi: 10.3748/wjg.v27.i25.3837.
3. Wang Z, Zhao Y. Gut microbiota derived metabolites in cardiovascular health and disease. *Protein Cell*. **2018** May;9(5):416-431. doi: 10.1007/s13238-018-0549-0.
4. Park EM, Chelvanambi M, Bhutiani N, Kroemer G, Zitvogel L, Wargo JA. Targeting the gut and tumor microbiota in cancer. *Nat Med*. **2022** Apr;28(4):690-703. doi: 10.1038/s41591-022-01779-2.
5. Nikolova VL, Smith MRB, Hall LJ, Cleare AJ, Stone JM, Young AH. Perturbations in Gut Microbiota Composition in Psychiatric Disorders: A Review and Meta-analysis. *JAMA Psychiatry*. **2021** Dec 1;78(12):1343-1354. doi: 10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2021.2573.
6. Cristoni S, Rossi Bernardi L, Larini M, Natale G, Didomenico N, Varelli M, Conti M, Dorna I, Puccio G. Predicting and preventing intestinal dysbiosis on the basis of pharmacological gut microbiota metabolism. *Rapid Commun Mass Spectrom*. **2019** Jul 30;33(14):1221-1225. doi: 10.1002/rcm.8461.